

Social Inequality in India, Social Development, and Globalization

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Abstract: In this paper I have tried to present the social inequality as a major cause of social tension and conflict in India, that have caused the decline of control and fall of order in the society. Using various data sources and literatures, it was found that India was having all five categories of inequalities, however main category of inequality was the income and wealth related. There was a tremendous gap in developmental and educational attainment by men and women and urban and rural areas. A wide inequality persisted between different states in terms of GDP and living standards. Inequality was contributed due to policies of compensating workforce working in the formal and informal sector. Even rates of compensation were directly related to profits and was not related to labor also caused basis for inequality in compensation. People working in government, industries, and market and urban areas were better compensated. It would be suggested to adopt a policy to compensate workers on equal terms irrespective of profits in both formal and informal sectors. States of the West and South were more prosperous in comparison to the states in the North and East. Education could have greater role in eliminating inequality, however, there was large inequality in educational attainment. Focus therefore should be on equal learning and adding value based education and education should be related to valued social produce, equal opportunities, and behavior.

Keywords: Social Inequality in India; Causes of Social Inequality; Challenges of Social Inequality; Equal Compensation; Equal Distribution of Resources

Introduction

Social inequality means exclusion. Patterns of unequal access to social resources are commonly called *social inequality*. It is a differential access to wealth, power, and prestige. Social inequality may exist on gender, race, age, ethnicity, religion, and kinship. By way of hegemony inequality may be sustained for longer periods. Hegemony is the domination of culture by one particular cultural group, resulting in the empowerment of certain cultural beliefs, values, and practices over others. Marx and Engels argued that the real basis of social and political inequality was property, and that since there was no private property in primitive societies, there was no state and no class or inequality. Inequality has become a permanent feature of rank and stratified societies. A stratification system where cultural or racial differences are used as the basis for ascribing status has been the caste system practiced in India. Castes are named, territorially delimited, and membership is determined by birth and unchanging. Caste is a rigid system of occupationally specialized, interdependent groups and has remained a fundamental social institution in India. The Caste system has been the main features of the Hindu societies, however, Muslims and Sikh communities also maintained a certain caste system despite departure from the Hindu philosophies and practices. Castes are ranked by purity and pollution customs, which used to organize political, economic and ritual life

Changes in educational attainment influenced inequality in India both favorably and unfavorably. In addition, changes in fertility can also contribute to inequality (Pieters, 2009).

The natural source of inequality in terms of age, sex, mental and physical conditions cannot be changed or altered.

However, inequality is not expressed in those terms. During the course of development people get classified into different classes and as a process of stratification amidst differences in status, power, income and wealth inequality is produced within the core of the society. Inequality has been regarded as a source of social conflict, tensions that may lead to decline of control, fall of order and values further leading to full or partial or temporary or permanent social disorganization.

Social inequality is the existence of unequal opportunities and rewards for different social positions or statuses within a group or society (Moffitt, 2017). Social inequality occurs when resources in a given society are distributed unevenly, typically through norms of allocation, that engender specific patterns along the lines of socially defined categories of persons (Wikipedia, 2017). Social inequality refers to the ways in which socially-defined categories of persons (according to characteristics such as gender, age, 'class' and ethnicity) are differentially positioned with regard to access to a variety of social 'goods', such as the labour market and other sources of income, the education and healthcare systems, and forms of political representation and participation (Walker, 2007). Basically, there are five types of social inequality such as political inequality, income and wealth inequalities, life inequality, inequality of treatment and responsibility, and inequality of membership (Farooq, 2015). Equality and inequality are not opposites; that equality is simply the zero point of the infinite range of inequality. The existence of inequality depends on socially recognized difference. The difference may often be simply a basis for socially imposed inequalities, as with ethnicity and gender, or it may be a real cause of inequality as with health differences (Blackburn, 1991). Social inequality is an area within

sociology that focuses on the distribution of goods and burdens in society (UIO, 2011).

Materials and Methods:

There are multiple methods of measuring inequality in different areas and different levels. Several secondary data sources has been used in this study to draw inferences. Some data sources are the National Sample Survey (NSS) data, OXFAM, National Family Health Survey, and Development-Educational Indexes. In addition, I have more and more relied on literature reviews, especially related to the quantum and theories of inequality. There has been certain international studies on regional inequalities in India in different areas and all such reports helped to a great extent.

Results:

There are various manifestations of social inequality. Poverty, deprivation, and gender gap are some of the manifestations in India. Since the economic liberalization in the early 1990s, the evidence suggests increasing inequality (in both spatial and vertical terms) as well as persistent poverty (Ghosh, 2007). There has been widening over-time inequality in the distribution of consumption expenditure, which is at odds with the impression of more or less unchanging inequality conveyed in some of the literature available on the subject in India (Jayaraj, 2014). Regional disparities increased in the 1990s, with the southern and western regions doing much better than the northern and eastern regions. Economic inequality also increased within states, especially within urban areas, and between urban and rural areas (Dreze, 2002).

All those five categories of social inequalities persisted in India to an extent, however, inequality in terms of income and distribution of income and resources or wealth is a major problem in India. The income inequality in Indian has been complimented due to inheritance, the system of private property, difference in natural qualities, acquired talent, family influence and destiny also (Seth, 2016). Large scale social inequality persisted in various terms even after almost 70 years of elapse of the colonial and feudal structures and democratization. Making a journey towards a welfare, democratic, and modern state India had abolished the *Jamindari System* however, that's not served the purpose of bringing social equality in India. At the time of independence there were very few industries and capitalists, however, at later stage large resources were accumulated by industries and capitalists. To make thing further worse international development initiatives and globalization also contributed social inequality by removing the barriers to open markets and the free flow of capital. Even a welfare and democratic governments in India also became part of those international development initiatives and the process of globalization and further contributed to social inequality. Government extra created their role and minimized the role of the respective society and community. Government almost became guarantor and contributor to the process of globalization, even without any application of mind considering that market forces would promote the economy, and the with developmental initiatives, especially in education, health, infrastructure, communication, and promoting social welfare by way of insurance, pension, unemployment benefits, student loans, soft loans to farmers they would establish equality in the society.

However, the same could not be the case. A large scale difference persisted in respective compensations in a formal and the informal sector. People working in the informal sector received much less compensation, salary, or wages in

comparison to the government and industries. Even within the government sector major discrepancies persisted in terms of contract and permanent employees, especially, in salary and other benefits. Under the influence of internal development efforts large scale employees were recruited on contractual basis in the government sector in the field of education, health, and other sectors and paid comparatively less to the permanent employees despite having similar qualifications and terms of works or duties. People working in industries and market were comparatively better compensated in comparison to the informal sector. In fact, it can be said that the large informal sector in the country has been made under privileged social groups and taking the loads of government expenditures and the globalized economy.

An economy within an economy was created by the policies of the government and that further sustained due to globalization and international development initiatives. The large structures of the government, industries, and market were not integrated with the larger social problems and objectives. Societies were deprived to sustain their values, philosophy, culture, and solidarity. The government repeatedly talked about the principles of inclusive growth, however, acted opposite to it. The government was having main role, such as to provide external and internal security, social welfare, justice, and connectivity, however, it created its role unwisely in many areas. Due to various provisions of the government acting unwisely and without application of mind various social groups most often came in direct conflict with those provisions and even a large scale of social tensions persisted among different social groups due to adverse policies adopted and propagated by the government, industries, and market.

There were several levels of inequality in the country, ranging from individual to social, local to regional and national to global. Even there were wide social inequality within a particular social group and also between one social groups to another.

Any process of development or globalization cannot superimposed from outside, however, any need for development as natural process must start from within the society. Therefore, the respective values, philosophy, culture, and solidarity of the society or community cannot be set aside or compromised considering it as a barrier. The education system also needed to complement those social values, philosophy, culture, and solidarity. Any development would be meaning less if it would not address the core social problem and objectives. The individual developmental objectives must coincide with the social objectives. However, amidst governmental and globalization, individual objectives were distinguished from the social objectives. In this manner a member of the society started fulfilling the objectives of other societies and nations, whereas his or her own society remained undeveloped.

There are a large scale variations in the amount of compensation paid to formal and informal sector. Even variations persisted in terms of industries, markets, national and international terms. If an e-tutor of India teaches students in the United Kingdom he is paid in Indian rates, whereas, if a foreign national serves in India through different structures of multinational or UN agencies they are paid as per the rates of their own country. Such variations in compensations by the industries and international agencies are one of the major causes of social inequality.

The government was having one of the major roles to avoid and restrict the accumulation of resources in few hands

however, government failed to do so. Therefore, large industries headed by large corporations and multinational companies functioned in India. Such large corporations may be permitted in some cases, especially where expertise needed to do research and development, however, most of the corporations and enterprises may be restricted, downsized, and made socially integrated with the respective social problems and objectives.

It would appear from *table 1* that upper caste Sikhs and Christians are more affluent than upper castes Hindus in both urban and rural areas. The affluence level of upper caste Hindus was at least three or four times greater in comparison to ST, SC, and OBC in both respective rural and urban areas. The gender gap persisted as exhibited in *table 2* in terms of life expectancy, savings, loans, and various levels of education and employment. Regional or state wise inequality in India has been exhibited in *table 3* in terms of growth and per capita state gross domestic product. Further, in *table 4* state wise difference in economic conditions, amenities, and social development has been provided that also reflects wide variations confirming a great degree of inequality among the different states of India. Lastly, in *table 5*, you can see the status of educational inequality in India, which has been in gradual decline. The same has also been demonstrated by *chart 1*.

Discussion:

India has done everything, however, not able to do what was required? Constitutional provisions of equality, equal rights, living with dignity have only served the purpose limitedly. Considering the fact that every person on this planet have also similar needs and therefore they needed to be compensated equally. Peace would only prevail if there would be equality among individuals, social groups, nations, and regions. However, it is more surprising that amidst so much activity by international development and globalists why such issues of equality do not make any concern so far. Social equality is an outcome of equal distribution of resources and valued social produce irrespective of intellectual and physical capacities, and without any consideration of races, sexes, culture, and age. If this would be accepted as principle first, then relocation and reallocation of resources and valued social produce may be arranged in global terms. Only then we would call it a true globalization. Inequality cannot be eliminated through a targeted action in some particular countries or their groups. It should be universal in nature.

Reservation in educational institutions, jobs, and democratic institutions why failed to end social inequality in India because they were never included however served a purpose in a selective manner. Still a wide inequality persisted among the same social groups and by benefitting some people never served the interest of an entire social group. Still, why political parties in India aren't taking inequality so seriously? Even land reforms and wealth tax would not serve the purpose. Even making a crackdown on the caste system would also not serve the purpose. Technological advancement, tech savvy people, and high growth would also not benefit the entire population equally. Therefore, the only alternative would be to reallocate and distribution of natural resources, wealth, and income appeared the sole remedies. Perhaps, this choice would irk many people, however, for the sake of majority the interest of a minority needed to be overvalued. People who would acquire talent and manage technology would certainly do better provided he also possess good physical conditions and there is peace in the society and territory. We cannot finish the family, caste, tribe and the market, however, certainly

control can be imposed against accumulation of income and wealth. Income and wealth are directly proportional to status and power. A total takeover of all wealth and resources by the government for the sake of their redistribution would not be easy, however, still government can impose policies of equal distribution of opportunities, income and in addition it can restrict the accumulation of wealth.

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Tables and figures:

Table 1: Percentage of affluent population in India (1999-2000)

Caste or category	Rural spending >Rs.1000 per month.	India Urban Indian spending > Rs.2000 per month.
Schedule Tribes	1.4	1.8
Schedule Castes	1.7	0.8
Other Backward Castes	3.3	2.0
Upper Caste Muslim	2.0	1.6
Upper Caste Hindu	8.6	8.2
Upper Caste Christian	18.9	17.0
Upper Caste Sikhs	31.7	15.1
Upper Castes Others	17.9	14.4
All Groups	4.3	4.5

Table 2: Gender Gap in India

Indicator	Female	Male
Bank accounts	26.5	43.7
Rate of employment in agriculture	59.8	43
Rate of employment in industries	20.7	26
Expected years of schooling	11.3	11.8
Infant mortality rate	44.3	43.5
Life expectancy at age 60, (years)	18.0	15.9
Life expectancy at birth, (years)	68	64.5
Loan from a financial institution	6.7	8.6
Ratio of males in primary and secondary education (%)	0.98	1.0
Secondary school education, gender of teachers (%)	41.1	58.9
Secondary school education, pupils (%)	46	54
Self-employed	85.5	80.6
Unemployment	4	3.1

Table 3: Per Capita SDP and Growth in SDP for Select States

STATES	Growth in SDP			Per Capita SDP		
	1997-99	2003-05	2007-09	1997-99	2003-05	2007-09
A.P	5.12	9.25	9.10	10160	13996	18001
Assam	1.32	4.90	6.36	6585	7602	8640
Bihar	2.47	5.48	14.11	3539	3992	5332
Chhattisgarh	2.90	10.26	8.10	8256	10412	12701
Gujarat	3.44	12.36	10.89	15613	20349	26447
Haryana	4.88	9.07	9.69	14742	20260	25110
H.P	6.74	8.06	8.42	11625	15590	19162
J & K	5.11	5.52	5.90	8601	9608	10696
Jharkhand	9.75	4.49	8.08	8448	9297	10967
Karnataka	8.32	8.95	8.44	11715	14518	18529
Kerala	5.83	8.46	10.00	10961	15339	20104
M. P	7.36	6.83	4.94	8759	9374	10204
Maharashtra	6.23	8.79	9.01	16494	20319	25190
Orissa	6.87	11.23	8.23	6466	8290	10309
Punjab	4.74	5.17	6.70	16320	18900	21603
Rajasthan	5.82	11.24	8.76	9708	11021	12862
T.N	6.35	9.78	6.75	13243	16663	21090
U. P	2.73	4.77	10.71	6452	7090	8573
Uttaranchal	1.43	15.28	7.52	8356	12844	16827
W. B	7.16	6.27	7.72	9827	12540	14929
Mean	5.23	8.31	8.47	10293	12900	15864
SD	2.28	2.91	2.04	3566	4814	6223

Table 4: The Composite Indices Articulating Three Different Dimensions of Development and their Correlations

States	Economic	Amenities	Social
Andhra Pradesh	1.12	0.98	1.10
Arunachal Pradesh	0.76	0.81	0.67
Assam	0.75	0.85	0.81
Bihar	0.72	0.58	0.66
Chhattisgarh	0.89	0.68	1.04
Goa	1.90	1.51	1.52
Gujarat	1.49	1.18	0.94
Haryana	1.20	1.05	1.05
Himachal Pradesh	1.10	1.13	1.50
Jammu & Kashmir	0.78	1.03	1.47
Jharkhand	0.82	0.58	0.75
Karnataka	1.41	1.06	1.44

Kerala	1.13	1.51	1.58
Madhya Pradesh	0.69	0.74	0.91
Maharashtra	1.76	1.25	1.31
Manipur	0.74	1.14	0.89
Meghalaya	0.77	0.96	0.78
Mizoram	0.79	1.52	1.00
Nagaland	0.83	0.95	0.95
Orissa	0.73	0.67	1.00
Punjab	1.45	1.22	1.38
Rajasthan	0.84	0.83	0.91
Sikkim	0.77	1.05	1.04
Tamil Nadu	1.17	1.15	1.17
Tripura	0.74	0.92	0.92
Uttar Pradesh	0.78	0.73	0.83
Uttarakhand	0.92	1.06	1.10
West Bengal	0.94	0.88	0.95

Table 5: Educational Attainment, percentage distribution

S. No.	Educational level	1987	1993	2004
1.	Illiterate	50.50	44.75	35.87
2.	Below primary	10.91	10.91	7.35
3.	Primary	12.46	11.00	13.23
4.	Middle	9.74	11.61	16.55
5.	Secondary	11.21	14.81	18.04
6.	Graduate and above	5.17	6.92	8.96
	Total	100	100	100

Chart 1

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